

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Amino Acids by Dichloramine-B in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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Kinetics of oxidation of several α -amino acids (AA) by dichloramine-B have been studied in aqueous acetic acid in presence of perchloric acid. The rates of oxidations show two ranges in $[\text{HClO}_4]$ with zero and inverse fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$. The reactions generally show second order kinetics in [DCB] in both the acid ranges and fractional order in [AA], although the magnitudes of the fractional orders are different. Oxidations of some amino acids have also been investigated in the presence of sodium acetate. Under these conditions the rates are independent of [AA]. The results indicate the participation of acetate ions in the reaction in addition to the secondary salt effect. Increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent decreases the rates of oxidations. Two-pathway mechanisms consistent with observed results have been considered. The coefficients of the rate-limiting steps at different temperatures and the corresponding activation parameters are also computed.

Oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is of interest both from a pure chemical viewpoint and from the point of view of its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism¹. Thus the mechanism of analogous non-enzymatic chemical processes of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is a potential area for intensive experimentation. As a part of our mechanistic studies with amino acids and other biologically active substrates^{2,3}, we report herein the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of a number of amino acids by *N,N*-dichlorobenzenesulphonamide in aqueous acetic acid both in the absence and presence of sodium acetate.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidations of Gly, Ala, Val, Leu, Phe and Ser by dichloramine-B have been studied in aqueous acetic acid both in the absence and presence of added sodium acetate. The results are shown in Tables 1—4 and Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (30%, v/v) AT 313 K

$I=0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4)$

$10^3 [\text{HClO}_4]^a$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})^b$				
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser
0.5	5.2	5.2	15.3	6.7	4.3
1.0	4.8	5.2	14.1	6.7	4.3
2.0	4.6	4.9	13.7	6.7	—
5.0	4.2	4.9	11.0	5.4	4.2
10.0	4.0 (11.2)	4.0	9.0	4.5	4.1 (7.5)
20.0	3.1 (6.2)	3.2	7.7	3.5	3.5 (6.0)
50.0	1.4 (2.9)	2.8	7.0	2.5	2.6 (4.4)
100.0	0.7 (1.7)	1.3	—	2.1	2.0 (3.8)

^a $10^3 [\text{DCB}]_0 = 50 [\text{AA}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. ^bValues in parentheses are at $10^3 [\text{AA}]_0 = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The reactions have been studied in 30% aqueous acetic acid. Rates of oxidations showed two

ranges in $[\text{HClO}_4]$ (upto $0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $0.005\text{--}0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The rates were independent of $[\text{H}^+]$ upto $0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and decreased thereafter with inverse fractional order dependence. The reactions generally showed second order kinetics in [DCB] and fractional order in [AA] (Table 4). Since the pseudo-second order rate constants slightly decreased with the increase in [DCB] for oxidations of Gly and Ala at low [acid] (Table 2), the rate dependences in [AA] with these amino acids were calculated from the first order, $1\frac{1}{2}$ order and second order plots of the oxidant. The magnitudes of fractional orders in [AA] computed from the three plots were almost the same.

Variation in ionic strength of the medium or addition of benzenesulphonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant, had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations, while decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the acetic acid composition of the solvent, decreased the rate.

Oxidation of Ala, Leu and Phe by dichloramine-B have also been studied in (1 : 1, v/v) aqueous acetic acid in the presence of sodium acetate. The reactions under these conditions showed only one range in $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and exhibited zero order in [AA] and zero to little fractional order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$. The rates increased with increase in [acetate] and the plots of k_{obs} vs [acetate] were also linear. Non-dependence of rate on [AA] under these conditions indicates the direct participation of acetate ion in the reaction, probably in the form of acylhypochlorate, in addition to possible secondary salt-effect.

The rates of reactions were measured at different temperatures in all the cases and activation parameters have been computed (Table 4).

Mechanism of oxidation: The probable reactive species in aqueous acetic acid solutions of dichloramine-B² are $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHCl}_2$, PhSO_2NHCl and

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS [AA] BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (30%, v/v) AT 313 K

$I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4)$

$10^3[\text{DCB}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³		$10^2[\text{AA}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³		$10 k_{obs} (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}) \text{ at } 10^2[\text{HClO}_4] (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$									
		Gly		Ala		Val		Leu		Ser			
		0.10	2.0	0.10	1.0	0.10	1.0	0.10	2.0	0.10	2.0		
Effect of varying [DCB] ₀													
0.5	2.0 (5.0)	7.8	6.3	6.0	4.0	13.9	9.3	6.7	3.9	4.5	5.9		
1.0	2.0 (5.0)	4.8	6.3	5.2	4.0	14.1	9.0	6.6	3.7	4.5	6.0		
2.0	2.0 (5.0)	3.7	6.2	3.8	4.0	14.0	9.3	6.5	3.8	4.5	6.0		
3.0	2.0 (5.0)	2.6	6.2	3.4	4.1	13.8	9.2	6.5	—	4.4	6.0		
4.0	2.0 (5.0)	—	6.2	—	4.0	13.9	—	6.6	—	4.0	6.0		
Effect of varying [AA] ₀													
1.0	1.0	4.0	—	4.2	2.8	12.6	8.0	3.9	2.5	3.7	—		
1.0	2.0	4.8	3.1	5.2	4.0	14.1	9.0	6.6	3.7	4.5	3.9		
1.0	3.0	—	4.4	6.5	—	—	—	—	4.1	—	4.8		
1.0	4.0	7.6	—	—	6.7	15.2	11.6	9.0	—	6.2	—		
1.0	5.0	8.9	6.3	11.3	—	—	12.4	—	5.7	—	6.0		
1.0	6.0	—	—	—	9.9	16.3	—	—	—	—	—		
1.0	8.0	10.9	10.8	13.3	12.9	—	—	—	—	—	—		
1.0	10.0	—	13.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	10.1	7.6		

^aValues in parentheses are for Gly and Ser at $10^2[\text{HClO}_4] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 3—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (50%, v/v) IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM ACETATE

$10^3[\text{DCB}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{AA}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10 k_{obs} (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			$10[\text{NaOAc}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10 k_{obs} (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})^a$		
			Ala	Leu	Phe				
Effect of varying [DCB] ₀									
0.5	2.0	1.0	7.3	6.2	6.0	1.0	3.6	4.0	3.2
1.0	2.0	1.0	7.1	6.3	5.9	2.0	6.0	—	4.6
2.0	2.0	1.0	7.2	6.4	6.0	3.0	7.1	6.3	5.9
4.0	2.0	1.0	7.2	6.4	6.1	5.0	10.4	8.5	8.2
Effect of varying [AA] ₀									
1.0	0.5	1.0	7.4	6.9	6.2	30	12.4 (11.0)	11.1 (10.5)	10.1 (9.3)
1.0	1.0	1.0	7.5	6.5	6.2	40	9.0 (8.9)	8.6 (8.3)	7.2 (7.5)
1.0	2.0	1.0	7.1	6.3	5.9	50	7.1 (7.0)	6.3 (6.3)	5.9 (5.8)
1.0	4.0	1.0	7.9	5.9	5.6	60	4.9 (5.3)	5.1 (4.6)	3.9 (4.3)
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]									
1.0	2.0	0.1	8.6	6.8	6.3				
1.0	2.0	0.5	6.9	6.3	6.0				
1.0	2.0	1.0	7.1	6.3	5.9				
1.0	2.0	2.0	5.4	6.0	5.5				
1.0	2.0	5.0	—	—	4.9				
1.0	2.0	10.0	3.9	5.7	3.8				

^aRate constants in the parentheses are recalculated from eqn. (4).

TABLE 4—KINETIC AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY DICHLORAMINE-B IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID

Orders observed in	In absence of NaOAc at $10^2[\text{HClO}_4] (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$								In presence of NaOAc				
	Gly		Ala		Val		Leu		Ser				
	0.10	2.0	0.10	1.0	0.10	1.0	0.10	2.0	0.10	2.0	Ala	Leu	Phe
[DCB]	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
[AA]	0.50	0.85	0.64	0.69	0.15	0.28	0.62	0.52	0.42	0.42	0	0	0
[H ⁺]	0	-0.90	0	-0.47	0	-0.27	0	-0.42	0	-0.32	-0.19	-0.04	-0.06
[NaOAc]	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.80	0.45	0.52
Activation parameters :													
	Computed from k_1 values ^a					Computed from k^1 values ^b							
log A	Gly	Ala	Leu	Ser	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser				
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	12.30	8.69	7.92	11.62	9.61	9.42	8.59	10.35	6.49				
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	67.8	45.0	41.9	65.1	63.3	60.4	56.8	66.8	35.8				
ΔS^\ddagger (JK mol ⁻¹)	62.0	43.1	40.0	60.0	59.9	57.4	56.8	57.4	31.2				
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-28.2	-84.9	-99.3	-39.2	-65.2	-74.4	-80.8	-77.0	-166.5				
	70.8	69.2	71.2	72.2	80.3	80.4	82.1	81.5	83.3				

^aValues calculated from eqn. (2). ^bValues calculated from eqn. (3).

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[AA]$; $10^3[DCB]_0 = 10^3[HClO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and (ii) k_{obs} vs $[AA]$; $10^3[DCB]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[HClO_4] = 1.0$ (Ala, Val), 2.0 (Gly, Leu, Ser). Solvent: 30% aqueous acetic acid, $l = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. 313 K.

HOCl. Amino acids exist in the cationic forms ($RCH(N^+H_3)COOH$, SH^+) in strongly acidic medium, which change over to zwitter ionic forms ($RCH(N^+H_3)COO^-$, S^0), as the pH of the reaction medium is raised and finally to anionic forms ($RCHNH_2COO^-$, S^-) in strongly alkaline medium.

Oxidation in the absence of sodium acetate: Oxidation of amino acids by dichloramine-B in aquo-acetic acid medium in the two acid ranges ($0.0005-0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $0.005-0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and in the absence of sodium acetate, may be explained by Schemes 1 and 2 respectively (two-pathway mechanisms, substrate dependent and independent paths).

Path 1:

Path 2:

Scheme 1

The related combined rate laws are

$$-\frac{d[DCB]}{dt} = k_1[DCB]^2[S] + k_2[DCB]^2[H_2O]^2 \quad (1)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_1[S] + k_2[H_2O]^2 \quad (2)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[AA]$ were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Fig. 1) in accordance with the rate law (2). The constants k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plots by inserting $[H_2O]$. Further, the $[amino\ acid]$ were varied at different temperatures (303–318 K) and the values of these constants were evaluated at each temperature (Table 5) and the corresponding activation parameters were computed from the plots of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ and $\log k_1/T$ vs $1/T$ (Table 4).

As the $[H^+]$ is increased beyond $0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the rates of oxidations showed inverse dependence in $[H^+]$. The kinetics (Table 4) under these conditions may be explained by a slightly modified mechanism, as under these conditions the equilibrium

becomes significant and the path-1 takes the form,

Scheme 2

The combined rate law (2) will then be of the form,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_3 k_1 [SH^+]}{[H^+]} + k_2 [H_2O]^2 = k' \frac{[SH^+]}{[H^+]} + k_2 [H_2O]^2 \quad (3)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[AA]$ (Fig. 1) and k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ (figure not shown) were linear in conformity with the rate law (3). Similar calculation of the constants k' and k_2 and the corresponding activation parameters were also made (Table 4).

As indicated earlier, the pseudo-second order rate constants decreased with increase in $[oxidant]$ with Gly and Ala under low acid conditions. Further, the pseudo- $1\frac{1}{2}$ order rate constants (computed from the plots of $1/\sqrt{[oxidant]}$ vs time) were constant at different $[oxidant]_0$. These results indicate that an additional competitive path showing first order kinetics in $[oxidant]$ may also be operative with these amino acids. The observed order in $[oxidant]$ therefore lies between 1 and 2 with Gly and Ala.

Oxidation in the presence of sodium acetate: Oxidation of Ala, Val and Phe by dichloramine-B in presence of sodium acetate showed only one range in $[H^+]$ and the rate was independent of $[AA]$ and $[H^+]$. Under these conditions, acyl hypochlorate formed from the interaction of oxidant and CH_3COO^- in the rate-determining step may react with amino acid in a fast step. These results may also be explained by a two-pathway mechanism (Scheme 3).

Path 1 :

Path 2 :

Scheme 3

Scheme 3 leads to the rate law,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2 + k_4[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-] \quad (4)$$

slight inverse dependence observed in $[\text{H}^+]$ may be due to the presence of the equilibrium,

A typical detailed mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by dichloramine-B is shown in Scheme 4.

The observed negative dielectric effect on the rates of oxidations is in conformity with Amis-Jaffe equation for dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interaction⁴.

Experimental

N,N-Dichlorobenzenesulphonamide, abbreviated

Scheme 4

The constants k_2 and k_4 were calculated from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-] 10^4$. k_2 (dm⁹ mol⁻³ s⁻¹): 2.6 (Ala), 3.9 (Leu) and 2.8 (Phe), $10^2 k_4$ (dm⁹ mol⁻³ s⁻¹): 6.0 (Ala), 4.0 (Leu) and 4.4 (Phe). The rate law (4) was further verified by calculating the rate constants as the solvent composition was varied, i.e. k_2 and k_4 were used to calculate rate constants at different solvent composition. The

as dichloramine-B (DCB), was prepared by the chlorination of chloramine-B and its purity was checked by elemental analysis, iodometric estimation of the active halogen and spectral data. A stock solution of the compound (~0.05 mol dm⁻³) in distilled acetic acid was prepared and standardised by the iodometric method. Chromatographically pure α -amino acids, glycine, alanine, valine,

TABLE 5—COEFFICIENTS OF RATE-DETERMINING STEPS CALCULATED AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (30%, v/v)

[AA]	k_1 (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹) ^a			$10^5 k_2$ (dm ⁹ mol ⁻⁸ s ⁻¹)				
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
	In the [HClO ₄] range, 0.0005 – 0.0050 mol dm ⁻³							
Gly	4.5	6.9	10.0	17.2	8.6	13.2	19.2	25.8
Ala	8.5	11.8	15.2	—	12.6	17.8	23.8	—
Leu	5.3	7.0	8.6	11.5	6.6	8.6	13.2	19.2
Ser	2.0	4.1	6.6	11.9	9.9	13.2	21.8	32.4
	In the [HClO ₄] range, 0.005 – 0.10 mol dm ⁻³							
	$10 k'$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)			$10^5 k_2$ (dm ⁹ mol ⁻⁸ s ⁻¹) ^b				
Gly	1.1	1.6	2.6	3.5	2.5	4.0	5.3	6.6
Ala	0.98	1.5	2.0	—	4.5	6.9	9.9	—
Val	0.68	1.0	1.3	1.9	28.4	34.6	42.3	50.1
Leu	0.95	1.1	1.6	2.3	7.9	9.3	10.5	12.6
Ser	0.51	0.66	0.82	1.0	14.2	18.2	23.5	29.8

^aValues calculated from eqn. (2). ^bValues calculated from eqn. (3).

leucine and serine (Sisco) were further assayed by the standard methods⁴. Aqueous stock solution (0.10 mol dm⁻³) of the amino acids were prepared in double-distilled water. Perchloric acid was employed as source of H⁺ ions. The ionic strength of the medium was kept at a high value (0.30 mol dm⁻³) using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate or sodium acetate. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements: The reactions were carried out in aqueous acetic acid both in the absence and presence of added acetate ions under pseudo-second order conditions, ([amino acid] ≫ [DCB]). The reactions were initiated by the quick addition of a measured quantity of DCB solution (in acetic acid), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a mixture containing appropriate amounts of amino acid solution, HClO₄, sodium perchlorate (or sodium acetate), acetic acid and water (to maintain required solvent composition), equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for nearly two half-lives by estimating the unreacted DCB iodometrically at regular time intervals. The pseudo-second

order rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within ± 4%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometries of DCB- α -amino acid reactions were determined in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of varying concentrations of perchloric acid (0.0005–0.10 mol dm⁻³) by equilibrating varying ratios of [DCB]₀ to [AA]₀ at room temperature. The products were found to be CO₂ and the corresponding nitrile⁶. It was further observed that the parent nitrile, methyl nitrile (CH₃CN) does not undergo further reactions with the oxidant under the present reaction conditions. Benzenesulphonamide (BSA), the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by tlc⁷ employing ether-chloroform-*n*-butanol (2:2:1, v/v) as solvent and iodine as detecting reagent ($R_f = 0.88$). The observed stoichiometry may be represented by the equation,

where, R = H(Gly), CH₃(Ala), (CH₃)₂CH(Val), (CH₃)₂CHCH₂(Leu) and HOCH₂(Ser). Addition of acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture did not show any polymerisation.

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